

Table S1. List of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) included in the study with their chemical structure, compound class, CAS number, and method limit of quantification (MLOQ)

CECs	Chemical structure ¹	Class ^{2,3}	CAS No. ⁴	Method limit of quantification (µg/L)
Methamidophos		organophosphate insecticide	10265-92-6	0.21
Omethoate		organophosphate insecticide	1113-02-6	0.10
Diazinon		organophosphate insecticide	333-41-5	0.12
Trichlorfon		organophosphate insecticide	52-68-6	0.26
Dimethoate		organophosphate insecticide	60-51-5	0.16
Acetamiprid		insecticide	135410-20-7	0.12
Phosphamidon		organophosphate insecticide	13171-21-6	0.17
Carbofuran		insecticide and nematicide	1563-66-2	0.075
Imazalil		fungicide	35554-44-0	0.12
Methidathion		organophosphate insecticide	950-37-8	0.085
Ethoprophos		organophosphate insecticide	13194-48-4	0.13
Carbaryl		insecticide	63-25-2	0.17

Linuron		herbicide	330-55-2	0.17
Malathion		organophosphate insecticide	121-75-5	0.22
Propiconazole		fungicide	60207-90-1	0.85
Sotalol		beta-blockers	3930-20-9	0.22
Acetaminophen		analgesics / antipyretics	103-90-2	0.12
Salbutamol		respiratory drugs	18559-94-9	0.13
Atenolol		beta-blockers	29122-68-7	0.10
Famotidine		gastrointestinal drugs	76824-35-6	0.17
Ranitidine		gastrointestinal drugs	66357-35-5	0.11
Propranolol		beta-blockers	525-66-6	0.11
Hydrochlorothiazide (HTCZ)		diuretics	58-93-5	0.12
Diltiazem		calcium channel blockers (CCBs)	42399-41-7	0.12

Carbamazepine

antiepileptic
drug (AED)

298-46-4

0.095

¹ ChemSpider [52]; ² EU Pesticides Database [53]; ³ Drugs.com [54]; ⁴ PubChem [55].

Figure S1. HRSEM image of pristine pyrochar.

Figure S2. XRD pattern of pristine pyrochar.